

**RE.
CAP**

Reinforcing CAP

PROJECT ACRONYM: RECAP

PROJECT NUMBER: 693171

PROJECT FULL TITLE: Personalised public services in support of the implementation of the CAP

WORK PACKAGE NUMBER & NAME:

WP.4 Deployment and Operation

DELIVERABLE NUMBER & NAME:

D.4.3. Intermediate Evaluation and Adaptation Report

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 693171.

Grant Agreement Number: 693171

Acronym: RECAP

Project Full Title: Personalised public services in support of the implementation of the CAP

Start Date: 01/05/2016

Duration: 30 months

Project URL: www.recap-h2020.eu

Deliverable Number & Name: D4.3. Intermediate Evaluation and Adaptation Report

Work Package Number & Name: WP4. Deployment and Operation

Date of Delivery: 27/06/2018

Contractual: 31 March 2018

Actual: 27/06/2018

Nature: R - Report

Dissemination Level: PU – Public

Lead Beneficiary: 1 – DRAXIS Environmental SA

Responsible Author: 10 – INI

Contributions from: INTIA, INO, DRAXIS

DOCUMENT HISTORY:

Versions	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
0.0	25/05/2018	V0	Draft for review	INI
1.0	11/06/2018	V1	Integration of comments	INTIA, INO, DRAXIS
2.0	12/06/2018	V2	Final documentation	INI

© RECAP Consortium, 2016

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Table of Contents

INTRODUCTION	4
1. Monitoring and Reporting System	5
1.1 Objectives	5
1.2 Methodology: specific tools and activities	5
2. Evaluation System	7
2.1 Objectives	7
2.2 Methodology: specific tools and activities	7
3. Adaptation of the RECAP Platform.....	9
3.1 Pilot Cases in the 5 territories	9
3.2 The Pilot in Greece.....	10
3.3 The Pilot in Spain.....	11
3.4 The Pilot in Lithuania.....	12
3.5 The Pilot in U.K.....	13
3.6 The Pilot in Serbia	14
4. Intermediate Evaluation and Results	15
4.1 Global timeplan and current situation	15
4.2 Intermediate evaluation and results in Greece.....	21
4.3 Intermediate evaluation and results in Spain	21
4.4 Intermediate evaluation and results in Lithuania	22
4.5 Intermediate evaluation and results in U.K.....	22
4.6 Intermediate evaluation and results in Serbia	22
4.7 Intermediate results at project level.....	23
4.8 Main findings and conclusions	24
APPENDICES	25
• Appendix 0: Initial structure of the Global Evaluation Questionnaire.....	25

INTRODUCTION

This report is the third Deliverable of WP4 “Deployment and Operation” of the RECAP project and presents the progress of activities related to the adaptation of the RECAP Platform within the 5 pilot participating countries (Greece, Spain, Lithuania, U.K. and Serbia) and the deployment and implementation of the Pilots.

With the aim of ensuring the measurement of achievement of the pilot objectives, as well as the evaluation of the user experience, specific systems and tools have been set up, according to the pilot plan (D4.1) and the global methodology which is described below:

Indeed, monitoring and evaluation activities of the RECAP Pilots are conducted across 5 pilot participating countries and mainly rely on a common methodology based on a i) *Monitoring and Reporting System*, for measuring the progress of the work performed within the Pilot Activities, and determining the achievement of the overall goals and outcomes of Pilot Activities; and an ii) *Evaluation System*, for addressing the different specific objectives of the evaluation.

This **Intermediate Report** presents:

- The **Monitoring and Reporting System** with its objectives and methodology;
- The **Evaluation System** with its objectives and methodology;
- The **Adaptation of the RECAP Platform and description of the Pilots** in the 5 territories;
- The **Intermediate Evaluation and Results at Month 23**, with the progress of activities in the different countries and the status of indicators at project level.

1. Monitoring and Reporting System

1.1 Objectives

A Monitoring and Reporting System has been implemented with the aim of i) **measuring the progress of the work** performed within the Pilot Activities, and ii) **determining the achievement of the overall goals and outcomes** of Pilot Activities.

1.2 Methodology: specific tools and activities

This Monitoring and Reporting System relies on the following **quantitative and qualitative tools** which have been developed for monitoring Pilot Activities and to be used by Local Teams in order to report on their Pilot:

i) Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that include different types of indicators:

- **Output indicators** that measure *activities directly carried out within the Pilot*, as a first step towards realising its overall goals. They allow determining the progress of work and act as *a first-level warning for potential problems* (e.g. problems in the adaptation of the RECAP platform).
- **Result indicators** that measure *the direct and immediate effects of the activities*, which will contribute to the achievement of the specific objectives of the Pilot. They act as *a second-level warning for potential problems* (e.g. low end-user involvement in Pilots, etc.).
- **Impact indicators** that measure *the impact of the Pilot in the frame of the project* and are related to its broader objectives (e.g. reduction of administrative cost for Payment Agencies, etc.).

ii) Monitoring Sheet in order to collect information on the status of Pilot Activities and monitor KPIs (mostly Output and Result indicators).

iii) Pilot Implementation Report in order to provide a detailed description of the different activities that have been performed for the Pilot implementation.

In terms of activities, the following Monitoring and Reporting Activities are expected to be performed in the frame of the Pilots:

1) Informing on the progress of the Pilots, the realisation of activities and the status of KPIs on a frequent basis. Each Local Team is asked to **complete the Monitoring Sheet** with data related to its Pilot **every 2 months**; and provide the **up-to-date status of KPIs at local level**.

2) Reporting on the progress and results of pilot activities twice in the frame of the Pilots. Each Local Team is asked to produce **two Pilot Implementation Reports** – an Intermediate report reporting all the activities performed at Month 23 and a Final report at the end of the Pilot Activities; and provide a **specific description and progress status of the Pilot**.

2. Evaluation System

2.1 Objectives

An Evaluation System has been implemented with the aim of **functioning as an early warning mechanism** and **addressing the different specific objectives of the evaluation** such as i) determining the satisfaction of end-users with the RECAP Platform and its services, ii) evaluating the extent to which RECAP is meeting the overall objectives established for the solution, iii) gathering effective feedback to enhance the RECAP platform, iv) getting perceptions and insights from end-users for future application (e.g. short term use, perspectives offered, potential for exploitation, sustainability, etc.), v) drawing recommendations to deliver more effective and efficient services, etc.

2.2 Methodology: specific tools and activities

This Evaluation System relies on the following **quantitative and qualitative tools** which are being developed for assessing results at project level or will be implemented by Local Teams in order to cover evaluation purposes at local level:

***i) Global Evaluation Questionnaire:** a set of questionnaires will be designed in order to evaluate the user experience with the RECAP Platform, and to collect a consistent basis of information to be explored more in depth with Focus Groups. These questionnaires will be based on a Global Evaluation Questionnaire, a common basis, which will cover all the different end-users groups (e.g. farmers, agricultural consultants, inspectors, Paying Agencies); and will need to be adapted to local needs and languages by Local Teams. With the aim of replying to the different purposes of the questionnaires, a first structure has been elaborated (**see Appendix O**): it will be reviewed and will be developed as a detailed self-administered form.*

***ii) Focus Groups:** specific events will be organized at local level with the different end-users groups in order to discuss deeply and validate findings from the questionnaires. These events and discussions, with a selected group of end-users, will focus on main aspects for ensuring the sustainability, transferability and wider take-up of the RECAP Platform, such as i) outlining the perceptions of the end-users on the RECAP Solution, ii) drawing recommendations for enhancing the Platform and its services, iii) identifying policy support scenarios, etc. Focus Groups will also allow obtaining “hidden” or unconscious information, which could be valuable information for Business Plan and exploitation issues.*

***iii) The Pilot Balance Score Card** that is made of a set of Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be frequently updated in order to follow the proper development of the Pilots, to assess the achievement of the expected outcomes and to measure the impact of the Pilots at project level.*

In terms of activities, after or simultaneously with the implementation of the Testing Activities of the different Modules of the RECAP Platform, the following Evaluation Activities will be performed in the frame of the Pilots:

1) Collection and pre-analysis of quantitative data on a frequent basis. Based on the monitoring and reporting tools/activities (Monitoring Sheet and Pilot Implementation Report), WP4 leader will update **every 2 months** the **Pilot Balance Score Card** and gather the following information:

- **Assessment of the success of the Pilot development** in terms of methodology and procedures followed (Output and Result Indicators);
- **Assessment of the impact of the RECAP Platform on the end-users groups** (Impact Indicators).

2) Collection and pre-analysis of qualitative data. Local Teams will use the qualitative tools – **Evaluation Questionnaires** and **Focus Group** – in order to collect information, update some of the KPIs (mainly Impact indicators) and gather mostly the following information:

- **Degree of satisfaction of end-users** with the RECAP platform;
- **Degree of accomplishment of the impact indicators** of the project (e.g. decrease in the administrative burden, etc.);
- **User perceptions:** potential demand of the RECAP platform in the Pilot countries, inputs regarding price and purchase of the service, insights for future applications and sustainability of the RECAP platform, transferability issues, etc.;
- **End-users views and potential recommendations** in the areas covered by the project as well as policy support scenarios.

3. Adaptation of the RECAP Platform

3.1 Pilot Cases in the 5 territories

The implementation and deployment of the Pilots within the 5 pilot participating countries (Greece, Spain, Lithuania, U.K. and Serbia) aims at testing and validating the RECAP Platform in an operational environment in different countries, with the active participation of public organisations, agricultural consultants and farmers.

The implementation of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) in these counties presents some differences and each territory has its own specificities. Moreover, depending on the country, the members of the project consortium involved in the implementation of the Pilots have different profiles and competences:

- In **Spain, Greece and Lithuania**, the pilot implementation will focus on the **public service delivery**, with the participation of 4 public organisations (INTIA, OPEKEPE, NMA and LAAS);
- In **UK and Serbia**, the pilot implementation will focus on the **delivery of personalised services**, with the participation of private companies (STRUTT&PARKER and INO) that offer agricultural consultancy services;

In comparison to the other Pilots, which are focused on CAP regulations (cross-compliance and greening inspections); the **Serbian Pilot** also presents a particularity since, due to the fact the only area payments distributed by the Directorate for Agrarian Payments with conditions similar to CAP are subsidies to support organic agriculture, its implementation will support the **entire process of subsidy provision for organic farmers**, certification agencies, agricultural consultants and for the public authorities tasked with implementing, managing and controlling this payment scheme.

As a result, the design of the Pilots has been made, taking into consideration all these particularities and specificities, and has led to the below 5 Pilot cases:

3.2 The Pilot in Greece

. GEOGRAPHICAL SCOPE:

The Greek Pilot takes place in **Larissa area** (Nitrogen Vulnerable Zone - NVZ), which is the capital and largest city of the Thessaly region.

This region is the most important agricultural area of Greece, and its heavy agri-production implies environmental problems, extra Cross Compliance (CC) rules and stricter CC requirements (Nitrate Vulnerable Zone).

. ORIENTATION/SPECIFICITY/FOCUS:

The Greek Pilot has been designed as a **support for public administration for a better implementation of inspection procedures of cross compliance**, as well as for the purposes of self-assessment for the Farmers, and stimulating new added value services for Agricultural Consultants.

The Greek Pilot is conducted by the only paying agency of the country (OPEKEPE). Therefore, the testing methodology is adjusted to this peculiarity.

. PARTICIPANTS:

Farmers and Agricultural Consultants, Inspectors (PA staff) and the Greek Paying Agency are directly involved in the Pilot.

In Greece, there are Consulting Bodies that assist farmers to apply for Basic Payment Claim (BPS) and Regional Development Program (RDP) measures which are certified by OPEKEPE. About 98% of the farmers apply through these Agricultural Consultants.

. TARGET OUTCOMES:

- ✓ **120 Farmers** will test the FARMER Module;
- ✓ **20 Agricultural Consultants** will test the FARMER Module;
- ✓ **3 Inspectors** (PA staff) will test the INSPECTOR Module;
- ✓ **1 Paying Agency** will test the PAYING AGENCY Module;

- ✓ **85 cross compliance inspections** will be carried out remotely with RECAP;
- ✓ **30 on the spot checks** will be carried out with RECAP;

3.3 The Pilot in Spain

. GEOGRAPHICAL SCOPE:

The Spanish Pilot is conducted by INTIA – the public company that provides public services for advising Farmers on CAP in Navarra; and takes place more precisely in **Valdizarbe valley** in the Navarra Media Region. The Pilot involves Farmers and Agricultural Consultants from the Agricultural Cooperative **ORVALAIZ** which benefits from services from INTIA.

This agricultural cooperative is relevant in the sector of cereals production, with more than one thousand CAP declarants; and which also presents other alternative crops and a small area with irrigated horticultural crops: WINTER CEREAL 70% 22,626 Ha, OIL CROPS 7% 2,390 Ha., LEGUME CROPS 7% 2,370 Ha.

. ORIENTATION/SPECIFICITY/FOCUS:

The Spanish Pilot has been designed as a **support for public administration** related to the CAP declaration: **cross compliance and greening inspections**.

All the functionalities of the RECAP Platform will be evaluated focusing on specific objectives. For instance, it will consider the potential establishment of an appropriate connectivity with other platforms (Sig AGROASESOR, SITUA, SIGPAC, AGROgestor) currently used by farmers and the cooperative, taking advantage of the digitalised information of the cooperative; and will pay specific attention on satellite images, since Remote Sensing is one of the most expected tools by farmers for the identification of crops and the variability of the plots.

. PARTICIPANTS:

Farmers from the cooperative, as well as its staff, are directly involved in the Pilot for testing and evaluating the different modules of the platform: Farmers & Agricultural Consultants, Inspectors, Paying Agency.

The inspection will be performed by INTIA, since it has been delegated to a specialised technician of INTIA. Nonetheless, the inspection authority of the Government of Navarra will participate in the pilot by taking part in the evaluation activities.

. TARGET OUTCOMES:

- ✓ **35 Farmers / 120 CAP declarants** will test the FARMER Module: 35 Farmers will test it directly. Most of them represent an average of 3-5 declarant farmers leading to 120 CAP declarants;
- ✓ **5 Agricultural Consultants** (3 from INTIA and 2 from the cooperative) will test the FARMER Module;
- ✓ **1 Inspector** from INTIA will test the INSPECTOR Module;
- ✓ **1 Paying Agency staff** from the Government of Navarra will test the PAYING AGENCY Module;
- ✓ **80 cross compliance inspections** will be carried out remotely with RECAP;
- ✓ **25 on the spot checks** will be carried out with RECAP.

3.4 The Pilot in Lithuania

. GEOGRAPHICAL SCOPE:

The Pilot in Lithuania is conducted by NMA, the National Paying Agency, and LAAS, the Lithuanian Association of Agricultural Companies; and is involving participants from the 10 regions of the country.

The following main crops will be tested: winter wheat, perennial pastures or meadows (5 years and more), spring wheat, peas, spring barley, black fallow, agricultural plant mixtures where protein crops are not dominant, winter triticale, clover, agricultural plant mixtures where protein crops are predominant, winter rye, buckwheat, beans, oats, spring rape, winter rape, pasture or meadow, perennial grass up to 5 years, corn, spring triticale, sugar beet, potatoes, winter barley, green fallow, herbaceous plant mixtures where protein crops are predominant, Lucerne.

. ORIENTATION/SPECIFICITY/FOCUS:

The Pilot in Lithuania has been designed as a **support for public administration for a better implementation of inspection procedures**, as well as for providing advisory services on the compliance with the CAP requirements (cross compliance and greening inspections) to farmers.

. PARTICIPANTS:

Farmers will be directly involved in the Pilot for testing and evaluating the FARMER Module (e.g. filling up farm data in the platform, etc.), through individual sessions with Agricultural Consultants.

Agricultural Consultants, Local Advisors from the Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service (LAAS), will be also directly involved in the Pilot for testing and evaluating both, the FARMER Module and the INSPECTOR Module.

Inspectors from the National Paying Agency under the Ministry of Agriculture (NMA) will participate in the testing and evaluation of the INSPECTION Module.

Paying Agency staff from the National Paying Agency (NMA) will test and evaluate the services and functions belonging to the PA Module.

. TARGET OUTCOMES:

- ✓ **150 Farmers** will test the FARMER Module;
- ✓ **60 Agricultural Consultants** will be involved in the Testing Activities (41 will test the FARMER Module and 19 will test the INSPECTOR Module) ;
- ✓ **8 Inspectors** will test the INSPECTOR Module;
- ✓ **20 Paying Agency staff** will test the PAYING AGENCY Module;
- ✓ **90 cross compliance inspections** will be carried out remotely with RECAP;
- ✓ **36 on the spot checks** will be carried out with RECAP.

3.5 The Pilot in U.K.

. GEOGRAPHICAL SCOPE:

The Pilot in the United Kingdom is conducted by Strutt & Parker and by the University of Reading; and is taking place in **England** only, with the involvement of Farmers from the whole country.

. ORIENTATION/SPECIFICITY/FOCUS:

The Pilot has been designed as a **support for agricultural consultancy in order to enhance services to farmers** for complying with CAP regulation and increasing the environmental productivity / sustainability of their holdings.

The main objective of the Pilot is to test the usefulness of the RECAP platform for UK farmers, but the inspector module will be also tested through the realization of On-The-Spot-Checks. The Pilot will assess whether the RECAP platform is (i) a source of guidance on cross-compliance for farmers and a store for documents for farmers to demonstrate their compliance; (ii) a detailed compliance programme which can deal with the real detail of cross-compliance, such as recording the locations of buffer strips, rights of way, splits in field geometry and other functionalities. The Pilot will test the individual functionalities of the RECAP platform and ask the participants to record the usefulness of them, as well as assessing the overall usefulness of the platform.

No other software is involved in the Pilot but the Local team will consider how the RECAP platform could be used with other software that UK farmers commonly use for agricultural management purposes, such as Gate Keeper and Muddy Boots.

. PARTICIPANTS:

The UK Pilot is focused on the end-user group of Farmers, which are directly involved in the testing activities. However, Agricultural Consultants will also take part of the activities and performed the inspections.

. TARGET OUTCOMES:

- ✓ **150 Farmers** will test the FARMER Module (10 in a practical test, and then 140 in a real pilot test);
- ✓ **50 cross compliance inspections** will be carried out remotely with RECAP;
- ✓ **25 on the spot checks** will be carried out with RECAP.

3.6 The Pilot in Serbia

. GEOGRAPHICAL SCOPE:

Organic Farmers participating in the Serbian Pilot are from the Northern province of Serbia - **Vojvodina**, and two municipalities from Central and South-east of Serbia.

Most of Organic Farms are from **Vojvodina** and the following municipalities:

- Subotica,
- Novi Sad
- Zrenjanin
- Sombor (Telecka village – group of organic farmers)
- Backa Topola...

2 groups of Organic Farmers are having farms located in **Central and South-east Serbia**:

- Blace Municipality
- Babusnica Municipality

. ORIENTATION/SPECIFICITY/FOCUS:

The Serbian Pilot has been designed as **a support for consultancy in order to enhance services related to the organic subsidy scheme**, and it is focused on the **monitoring of the entire process of subsidy claims for organic agriculture**.

. PARTICIPANTS:

Organic Farmers, Certification Bodies Staff and Representatives from the Paying Agency (Serbian Directorate for Agrarian Payments) are directly involved in the testing activities:

- **Farmers** fill all necessary data related to their farms and communicate with Certification Bodies and Agricultural Consultants;
- **Serbian Certification Bodies/Agricultural Consultants** test the usefulness of the platform together with Organic Farmers, and evaluate how can the platform fits in their regular workflow;
- **PA representatives** test the usefulness of RECAP platform as a support for organic subsidy provision, control of quantities of produced organic products. They will check Organic Farmers' entries. Local Team will provide them with information about Farmers' activities.

Certified Groups of Organic Farmers also participate to the Pilot.

. TARGET OUTCOMES:

- ✓ 75 Organic Farmers will test the FARMER Module;
- ✓ 45 Certification Bodies Staff will test the CERTIFICATION BODIES Module;
- ✓ 3 Paying Agency Representatives will test the PAYING AGENCY Module;

- ✓ 11 organic certification inspections will be carried out remotely with RECAP;
- ✓ 10 on the spot checks will be carried out with RECAP (with the support of Certification Bodies Staff)

4. Intermediate Evaluation and Results

4.1 Global timeplan and current situation

The implementation of the 5 Pilots is following the global methodology defined in the frame of the pilot plan (D4.1), which is basically relying on 3 main phases: Pre-Pilot phase, Pilot phase and Post-Pilot phase.

With regards to the calendar, according to the preliminary calendar, these 3 phases are taking place over a period of 15 months, during the whole duration of the WP4, as shown below:

PILOT DEPLOYMENT: phases and calendar	2017					2018										
	A	S	O	N	D	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	
	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	
Pre-Pilot phase	[Gantt bar showing Pre-Pilot phase from start to M23]															
Pilot phase	[Gantt bar showing Pilot phase from start to end]															
Post-Pilot phase	[Gantt bar showing Post-Pilot phase from start to end]															

Regarding the **Pre-Pilot phase**, at this stage of the project (M23), most of the preliminary activities have been performed and the training activities have been initiated by the different participating countries:

Pre-Pilot phase:	Greece	Spain	Lithuania	U.K.	Serbia
>> PRELIMINARY ACTIVITIES:					
. Setting up of local teams	1 team				
. Setting up of internal procedures (e.g. coordination and communication, technical support, etc.)	done	done	done	done	done
. Testing of the RECAP Platform (by the local team)	in progress				
. Training of the Pilot Team	in progress	in progress	to do	in progress	in progress
>> TRAINING ACTIVITIES:					
. Local Training Strategy	done	done	in progress	done	done
. Recruitment of participants	in progress	in progress	to do	in progress	in progress
. Training sessions for Pilot Participants	in progress	in progress	to do	to do	in progress

- ✓ Most of the Local Teams have been trained and have finished the testing of the RECAP Platform, but **additional training and testing** will be done in a second phase as soon as the last developments (e.g. the upload of the Remote Sensing results, Mobile application, etc.) will be finalized. In the case of UK, training and testing have been done by the core team, and will be extended to the rest of agricultural consultant team.

- ✓ Most of the Local Teams have defined their **Local Training Strategy** and initiated the production of their **Local Training Materials**. Some of the materials still need to be finalized and/or completed with further developments of the RECAP solution:
 - **Greece: 1 Manual** for farmers.
 - **Spain: 1 Manual** of instructions.
 - **Lithuania: none**.
 - **UK: 1 User Guide** for the platform.
 - **Serbia: 3 User Guides** (one for each end-users group).

- ✓ **Recruitment and Training of participants** have also been initiated by most of the Local Teams. Recruitment has been mainly carried out through invitations sent, the organization of dissemination workshops and contacts with local stakeholders and networks. The training of participants is still in progress in most of the participating countries; and, depending on each Local Training Strategy, mainly consists of workshops or training sessions organisation, individual trainings (face-to-face on site, online or via phone), etc. Local Teams are currently collecting, through the RECAP Platform, the **Consent of the participants**. So far, the following results have been reached:
 - a) **688 invitations have been sent** to (or contacts have been made with) potential participants: **285** in Greece, **155** in Spain, **40** in UK, and **208** in Serbia;

 - b) **291 potential pilot participants have been informed / trained** in the frame of workshops or training sessions: **170** in Greece, **18** in Spain and **103** in Serbia
 - **190 Farmers: 100** in Greece, **15** in Spain and **75** in Serbia;
 - **51 Agricultural Consultants: 40** in Greece, **1** in Spain and **10** in Serbia;
 - **31 Inspectors: 30** in Greece and **1** in Spain;
 - **15 Certification Bodies staff: 15** in Serbia;
 - **4 Paying Agency staff: 1** in Spain and **3** in Serbia;

 - c) **246 pilot participants are registered** in the RECAP Platform:
 - **171 Farmers (96** in Greece, **25** in Spain and **50** in Serbia);
 - **75 Agricultural Consultants (75** in Greece).

Regarding the **Pilot phase**, at this stage of the project (M23), most of the activities related to the adaptation of the RECAP solution for the different Pilots have been performed, the testing strategies have been defined, and some Local Teams have already initiated the testing activities with Farmers:

Pilot phase:	Greece	Spain	Lithuania	U.K.	Serbia
<i>>> THE RECAP PLATFORM IN THE PILOT</i>					
. Adaptation to the local context and specifications	in progress				
. Filling in the Farm details	in progress	in progress	to do	to do	in progress
<i>>> TESTING STRATEGY</i>					
. Definition and description of the Scope of the Pilot	done	done	done	done	done
. Definition of an operative procedure	done	done	in progress	done	done
<i>>> TESTING SESSIONS WITH PILOT PARTICIPANTS</i>					
. Testing the FARMER Module with Farmers and Agricultural Consultants (GR, SP, LT, UK, SR)	in progress	to do	to do	to do	in progress
. Testing the INSPECTOR Module with Inspectors (GR, SP, LT) . Testing the CERTIFICATION BODIES Module with C.B. staff and Consultants (SR)	to do	to do	to do	N.A.	in progress
. Testing the PAYING AGENCY Module with P.A staff (or similar) (GR, SP, LT, SR)	to do	to do	to do	N.A.	to do

- ✓ Local Teams are still working, together with DRAXIS and NOA, on the **adaptation of the RECAP Platform** to their local context and specifications. Most of them still have to integrate minor corrections and the further developments (e.g. Remote Sensing Component, Mobile application, etc.). Some Local Teams have identified major corrections to be made in the RECAP Platform before launching some testing activities; and they are currently working on with the technical team to integrate the modifications:
 - **Greece:** the workflow of the Inspection Module;
 - **Lithuania:** specific needs referring to local specificities;
 - **UK:** the workflow of the Farmer Profile.

- ✓ Regarding the **filling in the farm details**, most of the Local Teams are currently working on this activity:
 - **Greece:** the way to collect and transfer Farm data to the RECAP Platform is defined (farm data from the annual declaration of the farmer for BPS), but still have to be uploaded for launching Testing Activities;
 - **Spain:** the necessary resources are prepared and the transfer of farm data (annual declaration of the farmer) will be made as soon as the period of declaration will be closed (mi-may 2018);
 - **U.K.:** importing the farm parcel data and .shp files is being discussed. Due to the size of UK farms (typically over 100 individual parcels), a bespoke method of loading a farmer's field parcel data and field geometry is being developed.
 - **Serbia:** the farm data are being filled directly by the farmers on the RECAP platform. Organic Farmers/ members of the Certified Groups filled farm details in cooperation with Certification Bodies; and other registered farmers will do it by their own with the support of the Local Team.

- ✓ Local Teams have defined their **Testing Strategy**, with a clear description of the scope of its Pilot and its operative procedure:
 - **Greece, Spain and UK** are conducting their **Pilot in 2 stages**: a first stage, as a practical test, with a reduced number of participants; and a second stage, as a real Pilot test, with a large number of participants;
 - **Serbia and Lithuania** is conducting its **Pilot in a single stage**.

Regarding the **Post-Pilot phase**, at this stage of the project (M23), most of the evaluation activities have not been initiated yet. Some Local teams have just defined their Evaluation Strategy at this stage:

Post-Pilot phase:	Greece	Spain	Lithuania	U.K.	Serbia
>> EVALUATION ACTIVITIES					
. Evaluation Strategy	in progress	in progress	to do	in progress	in progress
. Getting feedback from Evaluation Questionnaires	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do
. Getting feedback from Focus Group	to do	to do	to do	to do	to do

The current report is presenting the progress of activities at Month 23; and at that moment, the development of the different activities related to the Pilot deployment shows that **the preliminary calendar with its 3 phases need to be reviewed** for different reasons:

a) **Pre-pilot phase:** in some cases, Training Sessions for Pilot participants show some delay; and this phase needs, in the case of the UK Pilot, to be extended. The UK Pilot decided to hold Training Sessions for Farmers simultaneously with Testing Activities through individual face-to-face sessions with Farmers and to wait for a version of the RECAP Platform providing all the required functionality for testing.

b) **Pilot phase:** Testing Activities also suffer some delay due to the fact that some Pilots needed more time than initially expected for the adaptation of the RECAP Platform to their local context and specifications. On the other hand, the Spanish and Greek Pilots decided to use the 2018 declaration in order to run the Pilots with up-to-date information and in realistic conditions and need to wait for the closure of the period of declaration to obtain the farm data (May – July 2018).

c) **Post-pilot phase:** Evaluation Activities which depend on the progress of Testing Activities will be done once the Testing Activities will be performed.

PILOT DEPLOYMENT: phases and calendar	2017									2018							
	A	S	O	N	D	J	F	M		A	M	J	J	A	S	O	
	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23		24	25	26	27	28	29	30	
Pre-Pilot phase	█			█					█								
Pilot phase	█	█															█
Post-Pilot phase	█			█			█						█				

Indeed, the **individual calendar of each Pilot** has been updated and is displayed below:

PILOT DEPLOYMENT: phases and calendar	2017					2018										
	A	S	O	N	D	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	
	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	
Pre-Pilot phase	[Green]					[Red]										
Pilot phase	[Green]															
Post-Pilot phase	[Green]					[Green]										
1. Pilot in Greece :																
Training Sessions						11/12	29/01	21/03								
Testing activities						[Blue]										
FARMER Module						stage 1		stage 2	A	A						
INSPECTOR Module									OL, OS	OL, OS						
PAYING AGENCY Module											R					
Evaluation activities						[Orange]										
2. Pilot in Spain :																
Training Sessions	WS															
Testing activities						[Blue]										
FARMER Module						stage 1					stage 2					
INSPECTOR Module																
PAYING AGENCY Module																
Evaluation activities						[Orange]										
3. Pilot in Lithuania :																
Training Sessions						OL										
Testing activities						[Blue]										
FARMER Module											OS/OL OS/OL					
INSPECTOR Module											OS/OL OS/OL					
PAYING AGENCY Module																
Evaluation activities						[Orange]										
4. Pilot in U.K. :																
Training Sessions						AC AC+F F F F F										
Testing activities						[Blue]										
FARMER Module						IF, IT, C OL, OS, C OL, OS, C OL, OS, C OL, OS, C										
Evaluation activities						[Orange]										
5. Pilot in Serbia :																
Training Sessions	29/09		11/10		06/11											
Testing activities						[Blue]										
FARMER Module						I I I I I I I I I I I I I I I I										
CERTIFICATION BODIES Module						I I I I I I I I I I I I I I I I										
PAYING AGENCY Module						I I I I I I I I I I I I I I I I										
Evaluation activities						[Orange]										

Spain, Greece & Lithuania Scenario:

- A: Application by farmers
- OL: On-line inspections by PA
- OS: On-site inspections by PA
- R: Report submission by PA
- C: Control/appeal by farmers

UK Scenario:

- IF: Data input by farmers
- IT: Data input by RECAP Pilot team
- OL: On-line inspections by consultants
- OS: On-site inspections by consultants
- R: Report submission by consultants
- C: Control/appeal by farmers

Serbia Scenario:

- I: Data input by farmers

4.2 Intermediate evaluation and results in Greece

At this stage of progress of the Pilot in Greece, training sessions have been implemented to Farmers, Agricultural Consultants and Inspectors through the organization of 3 workshops. These workshops led to the below observations:

- *Significant interest for RECAP and its services was expressed by the consultants. They search or have developed or have bought a tool similar to that (record keeping, registries, warnings for CC limits and notification for audits).*
- *Farmers did not show a strong interest. This is probably due to a) a low familiarisation with e-tools and b) different prioritization. They are probably much more interested in minor technical issue on the declaration of BPS.*
- *Agricultural Advisors are very interested in Sentinel results and layers (NDVI most popular).*
- *Agricultural Advisors are very pleased for participating in development of such a platform.*
- *Agricultural Advisors are interested to productively operate RECAP.*
- *All participants (agricultural advisors and farmers) have had smartphones. Most farmers have smart devices.*
- *Farmers during the sessions were not very interested in the functionality that allows farmers to see the inspection results after the inspector submits the results.*

Moreover, testing activities have been initiated with Farmers and Agricultural Consultants. From these first testing activities, the below comments have been underlined by the Agricultural Consultants:

- *Very useful for consultants.*
- *Rather difficult for farmers due to the low familiarization with IT in general.*
- *Great facilitation for electronic record keeping.*
- *Extremely useful for Nitrogen balance calculation.*
- *Useful for Information / Notifications for audits.*
- *Useful for non-eligible areas*
- *Free of charge is appreciated.*

4.3 Intermediate evaluation and results in Spain

At this stage of progress of the Pilot in Spain, there are no major findings as training sessions and testing activities with end-users have not taken place yet.

Nonetheless, based on the testing of the RECAP Platform with 25 claims of the same number of farmers for the first phase of the pilot, the below points can be underlined:

- *It is well appreciated to view graphically the 25 farms with their crops that have been loaded in the RECAP Platform.*
- *It is necessary to wait to see if the planned functionalities meet the expectations created. Undoubtedly, the pilots' realization phase will be intense and will allow identifying the necessary improvements.*

4.4 Intermediate evaluation and results in Lithuania

At this stage of progress of the Pilot in Lithuania, there are no major findings as training sessions and testing activities with end-users have not taken place yet.

4.5 Intermediate evaluation and results in U.K.

At this stage of progress of the Pilot in the U.K., there are no major findings as training sessions and testing activities have not taken place yet.

4.6 Intermediate evaluation and results in Serbia

At this stage of progress of the Pilot in Serbia, almost all the training activities have been implemented to the different end-user groups (Organic Farmers, Certification Bodies / Consultants and PA representative) and some testing activities have been initiated with Organic Farmers.

Based on these activities, the below feedback has been collected from the different end-users:

Organic Farmers:

- *The platform is a useful tool for simplifying the overall document management of organic subsidy scheme and certification process*
- *Difficult for farmers that are not very familiar with IT in general*
- *Organic Farmers that possess a farm registered as a Legal entity in Serbia, noticed that RECAP platform workflow was missing some information that are necessary for completion of their application process for organic subsidies. With the help of the RECAP development team, extra blank spaces for such information were added.*
- *Automatic creation of parcels by entering the cadastral number, will be very useful (farmers with more improved IT skills)*

Certification Bodies:

- Useful for the control during certification process – monitoring of certified quantities of organic crops
- More simplified documentation process
- Possibility for the record keeping
- Possibility to automatically create parcel by entering cadastral parcel number as perceived to be very useful
- Prevention of fraud (double) registration of one parcel by two or more certification bodies

Payment Agency (Directorate for Agrarian Payments):

- Greater control over subsidy scheme and each Organic Farmer
- Remote Sensing component as a very useful feature that could be exploited
- More simplified documentation process
- As a support for implementation of the CAP, they see the platform as a useful tool for future CAP implementation in Serbia

4.7 Intermediate results at project level

The Pilot Balance Score Card has been updated at **Month 23** (see *appendix 1*). The status of indicators corresponding to first range of activities of the implementation and deployment of the Pilots is displayed below:

INDICATORS	O = Output R = Result I = Impact	Target Indicator	Expected Achievement Time	Current Value	Achievement rate %
WP4: DEPLOYMENT AND OPERATION					
>> PILOT DEPLOYMENT PLANNING					
No of Pilot Plan	O	1	M16	1	100%
No of pilot teams set up	O	5	M16	5	100%
No of training guide	O	1	M17	1	100%
No of documents translated (e.g. training guide, mailing template for recruitment, informed consent form, guidelines for the organization of the training sessions, attendance sheets for the training sessions and evaluation questionnaires): 6 documents to 4 languages (Greek, Lithuanian, Spanish and Serbian).	O	24	M21	9	38%
No of pilot time plans defined (1 per country)	O	5	M21	4	80%
No of invitations sent	O	-	M21	688	-
No of participants having signed the informed consent	R	-	M21	175	-
No of participants informed on pilot time frame and procedures	R	-	M21	273	-
>> PILOT IMPLEMENTATION					
No of training sessions with Farmers / Agricultural Consultants	O	25	M25	5	20%
No of training sessions with Inspectors / Certification Bodies	O	10	M25	4	40%
No of training sessions with Paying Agencies Staff	O	3	M25	3	100%
No of Farmers having attended the training sessions	O	635	M25	175	28%
No of Agricultural Consultants having attended the training sessions	O	-	M25	50	-
No of Inspectors having attended the training sessions	O	-	M25	0	-
No of Certification Bodies Staff having attended the training sessions	O	-	M25	15	-
No of PA Staff having attended the training sessions	O	-	M25	33	-
No of Usernames & Tracking Number in RECAP for pilot	O	-	M25	246	-

4.8 Main findings and conclusions

The development of the different activities related to the implementation of the 5 Pilots, at Month 23, does not allow yet to define relevant findings and conclusions since main activities – Testing Activities and Evaluation Activities – have not been fully implemented yet by the 5 Pilots.

APPENDICES

- Appendix 0: Initial structure of the Global Evaluation Questionnaire
- Appendix 1: Pilot Balance Score Card (M23)

Appendix 0. Initial structure of the Global Evaluation Questionnaire

Part I. The satisfaction of the end-users with the RECAP Platform

I.1. degree of satisfaction with the tool:

- OVERALL SATISFACTION
- GENERAL ASPECTS OF THE TOOL
- PERFORMANCES / SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE TOOL

CRITERIA FOR
EVALUATION

I.2. degree of satisfaction with the functions and services:

- MAIN services related to the FARMER Module
- MAIN services related to the INSPECTOR Module
- MAIN services related to the S. CERT. BODIES Module
- MAIN services related to the PAYING AGENCY Module
- TECHNICAL Functions

I.3. degree of satisfaction with the results obtained:

- RESULTS

I.4. degree of satisfaction with the achievement of the initial objectives:

- INITIAL OBJECTIVES \Leftrightarrow CO-PRODUCTION (WP2)

Part II. The perceptions of the end-users on the RECAP Solution

II.1. perceptions on the short term use in the Pilot countries;

II.2. perceptions on the perspectives offered by the RECAP Solution;

II.3. perceptions on potential additional demand;

II.4. perceptions on the future use and sustainability;

II.5. perceptions on the potential impacts of the RECAP Solution;

\Leftrightarrow EXPLOITATION ISSUES (WP5)

CRITERIA FOR
EVALUATION

Part III. The recommendations of the end-users on the RECAP Solution

III.1. Recommendations for enhancing the RECAP Platform;

III.2. Recommendations for delivering more effective and efficient services;

III.3. Recommendations for ensuring the transferability and wider take-up of the RECAP Platform.

OPEN QUESTIONS

Appendix 1. Pilot Balance Score Card (M23)

Pilot Balanced Score Card - Overall

INDICATORS	O = Output R = Result I = Impact	Verification Means	Target Indicator	Expected Achievement Time	Current Value	Achievement rate %
WP4: DEPLOYMENT AND OPERATION						
>> PILOT DEPLOYMENT PLANNING						
No of Pilot Plan	O	Document	1	M16	1	100%
No of pilot teams set up	O	Internal Document	5	M16	5	100%
No of training guide	O	Document	1	M17	1	100%
No of documents translated (e.g. training guide, mailing template for recruitment, informed consent form, guidelines for the organization of the training sessions, attendance sheets for the training sessions and evaluation questionnaires): 6 documents to 4 languages (Greek, Lithuanian, Spanish and Serbian).	O	Internal Document	24	M21	9	38%
No of pilot time plans defined (1 per country)	O	Internal Document	5	M21	4	80%
No of invitations sent	O	WP4 Monitoring Sheet	-	M21	688	-
No of participants having signed the informed consent	R	WP4 Monitoring Sheet	-	M21	175	-
No of participants informed on pilot time frame and procedures	R	WP4 Monitoring Sheet	-	M21	273	-
>> PILOT IMPLEMENTATION						
No of training sessions with Farmers / Agricultural Consultants	O	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	25	M25	5	20%
No of training sessions with Inspectors / Certification Bodies	O	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	10	M25	4	40%
No of training sessions with Paying Agencies Staff	O	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	3	M25	3	100%
No of Farmers having attended the training sessions	O	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	635	M25	175	28%
No of Agricultural Consultants having attended the training sessions	O	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	-	M25	50	-
No of Inspectors having attended the training sessions	O	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	-	M25	0	-
No of Certification Bodies Staff having attended the training sessions	O	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	-	M25	15	-
No of PA Staff having attended the training sessions	O	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	-	M25	33	-
No of Usernames & Tracking Number in RECAP for pilot	O	WP4 Monitoring Sheet	-	M25	246	-
No of Farmers having completed the pilots	R	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	635	M30	0	0%
No of Agricultural Consultants having completed the pilots	R	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	-	M30	0	-
No of Inspectors having completed the pilots	R	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	-	M30	0	-
No of Certification Bodies Staff having completed the pilots	R	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	-	M30	0	-
No of Cross Compliance / CAP claims:	R	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	-	M30	0	-
No of Organic Certification Claims:	R	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	-	M30	0	-
No of online Cross Compliance inspections carried out in the frame of the pilot	R	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	305	M30	0	0%
No of on the spot checks carried out in the frame of the pilot	R	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	115	M30	0	0%
>> PILOT EVALUATION						
No of Global Evaluation Questionnaire for participants	O	Internal Document	1	M22	0	0%
No of set of Specific Questionnaires adapted to local needs and context.	O	Internal Document	5	M23	0	0%
No of Farmers having responded to the evaluation questionnaire (%)	R	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	75	M30	0	0%
No of Agricultural Consultants having responded to the evaluation questionnaire (%)	R	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	95	M30	0	0%
No of Inspectors having responded to the evaluation questionnaire (%)	R	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	95	M30	0	0%
No of Certification Bodies having responded to the evaluation questionnaire (%)	R	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	95	M30	0	0%
No of PA staff having responded to the evaluation questionnaire (%)	R	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	95	M30	0	0%
Number of user downloads of the mobile app	R	Application's management tool (DRAXIS)	5.000	M30	0	0%
Classification techniques can accurately identify cross compliance breaches	I	Accuracy level of classification techniques (NOA)	0,9	M30	0	0%
Reduction of administrative cost for payment agencies (%)	I	Pilot Implementation Report	25	M30	0	0%
Reduction of administrative burden for farmers (%)	I	Pilot Implementation Report	25	M30	0	0%
No. of agricultural consultants interested in RECAP platform	I	Pilot Implementation Report	470	M30	0	0%
- in the frame of the pilot activities (=> No of agricultural consultants interested in RECAP Platform)	-	Pilot Implementation Report	-	M30	-	-
- from dissemination and exploitation activities (WPS)	-	n.a.	-	M30	-	-
Nº of additional paying agencies interested in take up of RECAP	I	-	6	M30	0	0%
- in the frame of the pilot activities (=> No of additional PAs participating to the Pilot (except OPEKEPE and NMA) interested in take up of RECAP)	-	Pilot Implementation Report	-	M30	-	-
- from dissemination and exploitation activities (WPS)	-	n.a.	-	M30	-	-
>> PILOT DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES						
Nº of farmers informed about RECAP	R	-	9.600	M30	175	2%
- in the frame of the pilot activities (=> No of farmers having attended the training sessions)	-	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	635	M30	-	-
- from dissemination and exploitation activities (WPS)	-	n.a.	-	M30	-	-
Nº of farmer associations informed about RECAP	R	-	82	M30	0	0%
- in the frame of the pilot activities (=> No of Farmer associations participating to the Pilot)	-	WP4 MS + Pilot Implementation Report	-	M30	-	-
- from dissemination and exploitation activities (WPS)	-	n.a.	-	M30	-	-
Number of distributed printed/digital promotional materials	R	-	2.500	M30	262	10%
- in the frame of the pilot activities (=> No of distributed printed/digital materials in the frame of pilot)	-	WP4 MS	-	M30	-	-
- from dissemination and exploitation activities (WPS)	-	n.a.	-	M30	-	-
Number of articles/appearances in press and media	R	-	150	M30	19	13%
- in the frame of the pilot activities (=> No of articles/appearances in press and media related to pilot activities)	-	WP4 MS	-	M30	-	-
- from dissemination and exploitation activities (WPS)	-	n.a.	-	M30	-	-
Number of press interviews	R	-	5	M30	1	20%
- in the frame of the pilot activities (=> No of press interviews related to pilot activities)	-	WP4 MS	-	M30	-	-
- from dissemination and exploitation activities (WPS)	-	n.a.	-	M30	-	-